

ABOUT NATURE OF LASER-INDUCED SHOCK PROCESSES

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Abstract: *The main problems of nature the laser-induced shock processes are discussed. Along with acoustic shock processes, electromagnetic shock processes are also observed. The formal analogy between acoustic and electromagnetic shock processes follows from the specifics of the propagation of shock acoustic waves and Cherenkov radiation. The first process is limited by the speed of sound in the medium, while the second is limited by the phase speed of light in the medium. For the case of intense laser irradiation in the saturation regime of excitation, these considerations are also transferred to irreversible processes (instead of microvoids, nanovoids are observed in the experiment). If acoustic shock processes are characterized by the speed of processes that are greater than the speed of sound in the medium; then electromagnetic shock processes are characterized by the speed that is greater than the phase speed of light in the medium. That is why we analyzed the specifics of modeling and observing these processes in different media: solids, liquids, and gases. For this purpose, a cascade model of optical breakdown of the medium was used, which includes a modified Rayleigh model. The feasibility of using this model to describe and explain the presented experimental results is shown.*

Keywords: Cherenkov radiation, Rayleigh model, optical breakdown, Relaxed Optics, Mach cone, electromagnetic shock processes, acoustic shock processes, modeling.

1. INTRODUCTION

Main features the nature of Shock Processes and its place in Relaxed Optics are discussing/

Physics can be divided into several major branches such as optics, mechanics, electromagnetism, thermodynamics and more recent branches including general relativity or quantum mechanics [1]. The distinguishing feature of each of these branches is the type of material behaviour they are concerned with, and consequently, the various laws that govern that behaviour. Acoustic Shock Physics is part of Classical Continuous Mechanics [2], in which laws can be expressed as mathematical equations and describe the conservation of certain values such as mass, energy and momentum. The purpose of these general laws of mechanics is to explain how materials move when subjected to mechanical forces. More generally, mechanical engineers provide answers to the question “how does a material change shape depending on the forces (or stresses) applied to it?” If we were to give a very general summary, we could say that mechanics is concerned with the way materials are deformed when subjected to forces.

Shock Physics is concerned with the same phenomena, but with one fundamental difference: the time during which the stress is applied (force per unit area). In other words, in the case of an impact (vehicle against a wall, block of ice on an aircraft cockpit, bullet on armour, space debris on a satellite, etc.) or explosive, the material is subjected to

shock waves which transmit information about the stress imposed on a part of the material. The propagation times are relatively short, depending on the propagation speed of the shock waves within these materials. For example, in steel or aluminium, the propagation time (also known as velocity of propagation) is around 5000 *m/s*, in ceramics approximately 10000 *m/s* and in plastics around 3000 *m/s* [1].

The main characteristic of Shock Physics is therefore the dynamics of the phenomena encountered, i.e. the speed at which the material is deformed. The time scales dealt with here are microseconds or even nanoseconds. No need to be a genius to work out that a material will not react in the same way if it is subjected to forces for one μs or several seconds [1].

This is the real crux of Shock Physics: how to characterise a material's behaviour (deformation, damage, fragmentation) with respect to the intensity of the stress applied as well as the time during which it is applied [1].

In Relaxed Optics, along with acoustic shock processes, electromagnetic shock processes are also observed [1, 3].

The formal analogy between acoustic and electromagnetic shock processes follows from the specifics of the propagation of shock acoustic waves [2] and Cherenkov radiation [4-6] sound is limited by the phase speed of light in the medium. The speed of sound in a medium characterizes the speed of propagation of thermal vibrations of the medium, while the phase speed of light in a medium characterizes the speed of propagation of electromagnetic vibrations of the medium. In other words, these are characteristics of the collective motion of atoms and electrons and ions of the medium. For the case of intense laser irradiation in the saturation regime of excitation, these considerations are also transferred to irreversible processes (instead of microvoids, nanovoids are observed in the experiment) [1, 3].

If acoustic shock processes are characterized by the speed of processes that are greater than the speed of sound in the medium [2]; then electromagnetic shock processes are characterized by the speed that is greater than the phase speed of light in the medium [1]. Both the speed of sound and the phase speed of light in the medium are characteristics of collective acoustic and electromagnetic processes of the medium, respectively. From this point of view, there is a certain analogy, although the experimental implementations of these processes differ significantly.

That is why we analyzed the specifics of modeling and observing these processes in different media: solids, liquids, and gases. For this purpose, a cascade model of optical breakdown of the medium was used, which includes a modified Rayleigh model [1, 3, 7, 8]. the presented experimental results is shown.

2. MODELING AND DISCUSSIONS

Consider a stationary homogeneous gas flow that moves at a speed V relative to a stationary frame of reference S . If the speed V of the flow exceeds the speed c of sound in the gas (relative to the gas itself), then the flow is called supersonic; if V is less than c , then the flow is called subsonic. The properties of a supersonic flow are significantly different from the properties of a subsonic flow. In this regard, an important flow characteristic is the ratio M of the flow speed to the speed of sound in it [2]:

$$M = \frac{\bar{v}}{c}. \tag{1}$$

This number is called the Mach number.

One of the features of a supersonic flow is that small perturbations of gas density (and other quantities) cannot propagate in any direction in such a flow. Indeed, the speed of propagation of disturbances relative to S is equal to the sum $\vec{V} + v_s \vec{n}$, where \vec{n} is the direction of propagation of disturbances relative to the gas, v_s is s.p.eed of sound in media Therefore, all possible velocities of propagation of disturbances relative to S can be obtained if the vector is set aside from the fixed point O (at which the disturbances occur) and $\vec{V} + v_s \vec{n}$, if fixed V , all possible directions are given to the vector \vec{n} . As a result of such a vector change, the end of the vector $\vec{V} + v_s \vec{n}$ will be tangent to a sphere with radius c centered at the end of the vector V (Fig. 1) [1, 2].

Fig. 1. The emergence of a Mach cone. When a body moves in a medium at subsonic speeds ($V < v_s$), sound waves overtake the moving body; at transonic speeds ($V = v_s$), a density jump occurs in front of the moving body; at supersonic speeds ($V > v_s$), the enveloping system of sound waves forms a Mach cone (V is the flow velocity, v_s is the sound velocity) [1, 2].

Using Fig. 1, we can also explain Cherenkov radiation, we just need to change the speed of sound v_s to the phase speed of light c_{ph} in the medium, and the speed of the body to the speed of propagation of induced polarization in the medium [3].

Experimental data, which are included microscopic structure of optical breakdown in 4H-SiC (silicon carbide), are represented in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 [9, 10]. Sectional area of receiving structures was $\sim 22 \mu m$, the depth of $\sim 50 \mu m$. As seen from Fig. 2 (c) we have five stages disordered regions, which are located at a distance from 2 to 4 μm apart vertically [9, 10]. Branches themselves in this case have a thickness from 150 to 300 nm. In this case there are lines in the irradiated nanocavity with spherical diameter of from 10 nm to 20 nm. In this case irradiated structures have crystallographic symmetry of the initial structure.

In this case diffraction processes may be generated in two stages: 1- formation of diffraction rings of focused beams [9, 10] and second-formation of diffracting gratings in the time of redistribution of second-order Cherenkov radiation [3]. Second case is analogous to the creation of self-diffraction gratings in Nonlinear Optics, but for Fig. 2 (c) and Fig. 3 (b) our gratings are limited by Mach cone of Cherenkov radiation. Roughly speaking only Fig 2 (e) and Fig. 3 are represented “clean” shork processes (breakdown) [3].

Since the initial radiation is focusing, it causes the occurrence of heterogeneous polarization of the medium, which in turn is the source of generation of a whole range of non-linear optical effects, which leads to a continuous spectrum [3, 6]. However, since the cone of initial radiation is transformed into a set of diffractionally stratified cones of

heterogeneous polarization of the medium. Then the radiation occurs inside the cones, the generators of which are perpendicular to the generator cones of polarization. In addition, this, according to [6, 11], is Cherenkov radiation.

Fig 2. (a) Schematic illustration of the laser irradiated pattern. The light propagation direction (k) and electric field (E) are shown. (b) Optical micrograph of the mechanically thinned sample to show cross sections of laser-irradiated lines (200 nJ/pulse). (c) Bright-field TEM image of the cross section of a line written with pulse energy of 300 nJ/pulse . (d) Schematic illustration of a geometric relationship between the irradiated line and the cross-sectional micrograph. (e) Magnified image of a rectangular area in (c) [9, 10].

Fig. 3. Laser-modified layers with a spacing of 150 nm are indicated by arrows. (a) Bright-field TEM image of a portion of the cross section of a line written with a pulse energy of 200 nJ/pulse . (b) Zero-loss image of a same area as in (a) with nanovoids appearing as bright areas. Correspondence with (a) is found by noting the arrowheads in both micrographs. (c) Schematic illustrations of the microstructure of a laser modified line. Light-propagation direction (k), electric field (E), and scan direction (SD) are shown. Only two groups (groups I and II) of the laser-modified microstructure are drawn [9, 10].

For the explanation of experimental data of Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 were used next cascade of processes: diffraction stratification of initial radiation; generation of Cherenkov radiation;

interference of short wave this Cherenkov radiation and optical breakdown in the maximum of corresponding interferogram [3].

The estimation of sizes the cascade of volume destructions of Fig. 2 c) may be explains in next way [1]. The sizes (diameters) of proper stages d_{nir} of cascade are proportionally to corresponding diffraction diameters d_{ndif}

$$d_{nir} = k d_{ndif}, \tag{2}$$

where k is the proportionality constant.

The diffraction diameters d_{ndif} may be determined with help condition of diffraction-pattern lobes (modified Rayleigh ratio)

$$d_{ndif} = n\lambda. \tag{3}$$

The estimations of first five diffraction diameters d_{ndif} for $\lambda = 800 \text{ nm}$ were represented in [3].

Cherenkov angle may be determined from next formula [3]

$$\theta_{ch} + \alpha_{ir} = \pi/2 \text{ or } \theta_{ch} = \pi/2 - \alpha_{ir}, \tag{4}$$

where α_{ir} – angle between tangent line and direction of laser beam (focusing angle).

Last formula was receiving on the basis A. Bohr microscopic theory of Cherenkov radiation. According this theory each electron has own zone of influence of irradiated media (A. Bohr hiperboloid, Fig. 4 [11]).

Fig. 4. To explanation of a deceleration of particle in matter (A. Bohr hyperboloid) [11].

Now we receive an estimation of interaction of electron, which is placed in point Q and collided with particle Z that is transmitted on distance ρ (Fig. 4) [11].

Simultaneously other accelerated electrons mainly in time $t' = t - \frac{r}{c}$ after a collision from this particle. An electron in point A in moment t' was placed in phase of co-collision, which is advanced on time τ the phase of co-collision in point Q. A time τ is equaled [11]

$$\tau = \frac{r}{c} - \frac{x}{v} \tag{5}$$

where v – a velocity of particle, x – a projection of distance QA on the direction of motion.

Introductive $r^2 = x^2 + b^2$ we received from formula (5) next correlation [11]

$$\frac{(x+v\tau\gamma^2)^2}{v^2\tau^2\gamma^2(\gamma^2-1)} - \frac{b^2}{c^2\tau^2(\gamma^2-1)} = 1. \tag{6}$$

Where $\gamma = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)^{-1/2}$.

Generally speaking, the Bohr hyperboloid can be considered as a hyperboloid of the polarization of the medium [3, 11]. Under appropriate conditions, the generators of the Cherenkov radiation cone are perpendicular to the surface of the hyperboloid. Moreover, this applies to each incident particle. In the case of irradiation with focused laser

radiation, the role of O. Bohr hyperboloids is played by diffraction stratified cones of focused laser radiation [3]. If for electrons the number of cones (hyperboloids) is determined by the number of incident particles, then for focused laser radiation - by the number of stratified cones (this is confirmed by the experimental results of Fig. 2). In this case, the generators of the Cherenkov radiation cones will be perpendicular to the generating diffraction cones [3]. And thus we have optically induced Cherenkov radiation, the photon efficiency of which is $\sim 0.2 - 0.5$, while for classical Cherenkov radiation $\sim 10^{-7} - 10^{-5}$. For the optical case, we have that the radiation energy goes mainly to the polarization of the medium, while when irradiated with high-energy particles, the main part of the energy goes to radiation defect formation (displacement of atoms, etc.) [1, 3].

It should be noted that laser-induced continuous and cone radiation is nothing more than optically induced Cherenkov radiation [1,3, 6, 12].

It was noted that cone radiation has a surface structure. From our point of view, this is explained by the fact that the main role in the formation of Cherenkov radiation is played by diffraction cones [1, 3]. The polarization processes that lead to Cherenkov radiation occur in the near-surface regions of these cones, therefore the resulting radiation has a surface nature [3].

We can rough estimate basic peculiarities of energy distribution in Mach cone may be used next formula [3]

$$E_{1ob} = \frac{\pi^2}{4} (\sum_{i=1}^5 n_{iav}^2 l_{iav}) r^2 N_{asic} E_{Zth}, \tag{7}$$

where n_{iav} – average visible number of filaments in proper group of cascade, $l_{iav}=1000 \text{ nm}$ – average length of filaments in proper group of cascade, $r = 10 \text{ nm}$ – average radius of filament, N_a – atom density of 4H-SiC.

For further estimation we use next approximation $n_{1av} = n_{2av} = n_{3av} = n_{4av} = n_{5av} = 100$, (see Fig. 2 c) [3].

Energy, which is necessary for the optical breakdown our nanotubes may be determined in next way. Zeitz threshold energy for 4H-SiC is equaled $E_{Zth} \sim 25 \text{ eV}$ [3]. Let this value is corresponded to energy of optical breakdown. Therefore, summary energy E_{1ob} is equaled

$$E_{1ob} = N_{asnt} \cdot E_{Zth} = 23.2 \text{ nJ}. \tag{8}$$

This value is equaled of $\sim 8\%$ from pulse energy or $\sim 30\%$ from the effective absorbed energy of pulse [3]. In this case we have more high efficiency of transformation initial radiation to “irreversible” part of Cherenkov radiation. It is result of more intensive excitation comparatively with classical methods of receiving the Cherenkov radiation. In this case, we have pure photochemical processes. The experimental data for intrinsic absorption [3] show that for short pulse regime of irradiation (femtosecond regime) basic processes of destruction the fused silica and calcium fluoride are photochemical (multiphoton absorption in the regime of saturation the excitation). However, basic peculiarity of experimental data Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 is transformation the initial laser radiation (wavelength 800 nm) to continuum Cherenkov radiation. From length of optical breakdown in 4H-SiC we can determine average absorption index of Cherenkov radiation. It is $\sim 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This value is corresponded to violet-blue range of absorption spectrum of 4H-SiC [3].

For the estimations of maximal radius of nanovoids we must use modified Rayleigh formula [1, 3, 7, 8]

$$R_{max} = \frac{2R}{0.915r} \sqrt{\frac{E_{ir}}{\pi \tau_{ir} c E}}, \tag{9}$$

where T_c – the time of creation the nanovoid (bubble), R is radius of nanovoid, r – radius of irradiated zone, E – Young module, E_{ir} – energy of one pulse. τ_{ir} – duration of pulse [3]

If we substitute $r = 250 \text{ nm}$, $R = 10 \text{ nm}$, $E=600 \text{ GPa}$ [3], $E_{ir}=300 \text{ nJ}$, $\tau_{ir} = 130 \text{ fs}$, $c=3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$, than have $R_{max}=11 \text{ nm}$ [3].

The speed of shock waves for femtosecond regime of irradiation is less as speed of sound. However, we have two speeds of sound in elastic body: longitudinal v_{ls} and transversal v_{ts} [3]. Its values are determined with next formulas

$$v_{ls} = \sqrt{\frac{E(1-\nu)}{\rho_0(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)}}, \text{ and } v_{ts} = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho_0(1+\nu)}} \quad (10)$$

where ν – Poisson’s ratio [65, 66]. The ratio between of these two speeds is equaled

$$\alpha = \frac{v_{ts}}{v_{ls}} = \sqrt{\frac{(1-2\nu)}{2(1-\nu)}} \quad (11)$$

However, this ratio must be true for shock waves too. Therefore, for silicon carbide for $\nu = 0,45$ [3] $\alpha = 0,33$. Roughly speaking last ratio is determined the step of ellipsoidal forms of our nanovoids (Fig. 3(c)).

Formulas (10) allow estimating maximal longitudinal and transversal $R_{max,i}, i \in (l, t)$. These values are 6 nm and 19 nm properly for SiC [3].

In a similar manner, the results of the optical detection of potassium chloride when irradiated with nanosecond pulses of a CO₂ laser [11] were evaluated.

Laser-induced optical breakdown was researched in [1, 3, 11]]. Two damages region in a crystal with moderately high density of inclusions were received in [65, 66] for potassium chloride after irradiation by CO₂-laser pulses (wavelength 10.6 μm, duration of pulse 30 ns). The laser was known to be operating in the lowest-order transverse Gaussian mode. There were several longitudinal modes, however, which contributed a time structure to the pulse, periodic at the cavity round-trip time. The phase relationships between the longitudinal modes varied from shot to shot, changing the details of the time structure and causing the peak of the envelope to fluctuate by ±15% [11]. These results are presented in Fig. 4 [11].

Fig 5. Two damages region in a crystal KCl with moderately high density of inclusions. The round black objects are bubbles. The radiation, incident from left to right, was just at the intrinsic breakdown threshold. In one case (a) there was damage only at the inclusions. In (b), intrinsic breakdown occurred as evidenced by the pointed bubble. The straight lines represent cleavage [11].

Successive laser shot (1/sec) were focused into bulk single crystals using a 1-inch focal length “Irtran 2” lens. The breakdown was monitored by observing the visible light from the focal region and by examining the damaged region under the microscope. It was found that most of the crystals suffered some damage even at relatively low power levels. The threshold of this type of damage varied by an order magnitude from one position in the crystal to another. At any particular energy level, damage would occur on the first laser shot or not at all. Fig. 5 (a) shows that spatial inhomogeneities are in fact inclusions [11]. The damage bubbles occur randomly near, not necessarily in, the tiny focal volume. At a well-defined power threshold, an elongated pointed bubble forms, its vertex falling at the focus (Fig. 5 (b)). This power level is regarded as the bulk intrinsic breakdown threshold. Its value is reproducible in crystals from different manufacturers, with inclusions or without. When no inclusion free samples of a compound were available, the considerations mentioned above were used to determine the dielectric strength [11].

Let us take the ratio of the radius of the irradiation zone to the radius of the nanowire as 50 [13]. The energy of irradiation is 2 J. The duration of irradiation is 30 ns, mode of CO₂-laser irradiation is TEM₀₁ [13]. Young's modulus 29.67 GPa, Poisson's ratio 0.216 [3]. In this case, due to the mode structure of the irradiation, we had two breakdown channels, each with ~ 7 cascade members [13]. However, we do not see the microscopic breakdown structure here due to the low resolution of the optical photograph compared to the TEM images of Fig. 2 and Fig.3. Experimental data for KCl [13] and for SiC (Fig. 2 c) have similar appearance [3].

Therefore, in a similar manner, the results of the optical breakdown of potassium chloride when irradiated with nanosecond pulses of a CO₂ laser [13] were evaluated. After substitution corresponding data to formula (9) we have $R_{maxKCl} = 62.5nm$ [3]. Ellipticity of KCl nanovoids may be determined from (11) $\alpha_{KCl} = 0.6$ [3].

Let us now estimate the maximum bubble radii for the acoustic case. For this, in formula (9), you need to change the speed of light to the speed of sound (9 a).

$$R_{max}^{ac} = \frac{2R}{0.915r} \sqrt{\frac{E_{ir}}{\pi \tau_{ir} c_s E}} \tag{9 a}$$

where c_s is speed of sound.

As a result, we get $R_{maxSiC}^{ac} = 1.7\mu m$ and $R_{maxKCl}^{ac} = 28\mu m$ [1, 3]. The shape of the voids does not change, they just increase in size by 2-3 orders of magnitude.

If we take the ratio of the acoustic formula (9 a) and the optical formula (9), then for the same irradiation modes we have the ratio

$$\frac{R_{max}^{ac}}{R_{max}} = \sqrt{\frac{c}{c_s}} \tag{12}$$

However, a comparison with the experimental results (Fig. 3) shows that the main role in the formation of nanovoids have mainly electromagnetic processes. This is explained by the fact that in this case a chain of close-range coherent processes of transformation of both optical radiation into the excitation of the medium and the corresponding relaxation of the medium is implemented, in other words, there is a chain of interconnected coherent transformations.

To estimate the size of laser-induced micro- or nanowires in liquids and gases [12, 14], we can also use formula (9), in which we need to replace Young's modulus E with the compressibility modulus K of the medium [1].

We have for electromagnetic case the next formula

$$R_{maxel} = \frac{2R}{0.915r} \sqrt{\frac{E_{ir}}{\pi \tau_{ir} c R^2}} \tag{9 b}$$

and the acoustic case

$$R_{maxac} = \frac{2R}{0.915r} \sqrt{\frac{E_{ir}}{\pi\tau_{ir}c_p K}} \tag{9 c}$$

Therefore, we have

$$\frac{R_{maxliq}}{R_{maxsol}} \sim \sqrt{\frac{K}{E}} \tag{13}$$

So, for equivalence regimes of irradiation

$$\frac{R_{maxH_2O}}{R_{maxSiC}} \sim \sqrt{\frac{600}{2.2}} = 16.51, \tag{13 a}$$

and

$$\frac{R_{maxH_2O}}{R_{maxKCl}} \sim \sqrt{\frac{29.67}{2.2}} = 3.67. \tag{13 b}$$

A compressibility modulus K for H_2O is equaled 2.2 Gpa [15], and for air 10^{-4} Gpa [16]. Therefore,

$$\frac{R_{maxair}}{R_{maxSiC}} \sim \sqrt{\frac{600}{10^{-4}}} = 2450. \tag{13 c}$$

Thus estimating sizes “electromagnetic” water and air voids (radiuses) are equaled 165 nm for water and $24.5 \mu\text{m}$ for air. Corresponding “acoustic” radiuses are equaled $\sim 74 \mu\text{m}$ for water and $\sim 22.9 \text{ mm}$ for air.

Table 1 shows the experimental results for water irradiated with femtosecond lasers with a duration of 340 fs at different wavelengths [14].

Table 1. for fs optical breakdown in water (340 fs) at different wavelengths λ and NA (numerical aperture), with focal radius $r = 0.61\lambda/NA$. The threshold values include the breakdown energy E_{th} (50% breakdown probability), irradiance I_{th} , threshold sharpness $S = E_{th}/\Delta E$ where ΔE denotes the interval between 10% and 90% breakdown probability, and the bubble size R_{max} at threshold [14].

$\lambda, \text{ nm}$	NA	$r, \text{ nm}$	$E_{th}, \text{ nJ}$	$I_{th} \cdot 10^{12} \text{ W/cm}^2$	S	$R_{max}, \text{ nm}$
1040	0.8	793	22.6	3.37	30.5	328 ± 44
1040	0.9	705	18.5	3.49	18.9	322 ± 96
520	0.8	397	4.79	2.85	62.3	288 ± 28
520	0.9	353	4.20	3.17	67.8	232 ± 17
347	0.8	264	3.95	5.29	47.1	216 ± 17
347	0.9	235	3.78	6.40	52.2	190 ± 9

As can be seen from Table 1, the maximum radii are in satisfactory agreement with the “electromagnetic” theoretical estimates.

As we can see, the modified Rayleigh model has general nature and may be applied to estimate the size of voids in all condensed media.

Based on the data in Table 1, it can also be concluded that the decrease in the maximum radius of voids (bubbles) with decreasing wavelength may be due to a decrease in the geometric dimensions of diffraction-stratified cones, and at the same time, Cherenkov cones, and a shift of the Cherenkov radiation spectra into a more short-wave region.

Thus, in all three cases (silicon carbide, potassium chloride, and water) we have the electromagnetic nature of the optical breakdown, which has complex structure (generation optical-induced Cherenkov radiation and formation of voids) i.e., shock processes.

3. CONCLUSIONS

1. Main features and comparative qanalysis of acoustic and electromagnetic shock processes are observing.
2. Formal similarities and differences between acoustic shock waves and Cherenkov radiation are showing.

3. Some aspects of A. Bohr microscopic mechanism of Cherenkov radiation and its application for optical case are discussing.
4. The universality of the modified Rayleigh model has been testing for acoustic and electromagnetic shock processes.
5. The presented experimental results on pulsed laser-induced optical breakdown of silicon carbide, potassium chloride, and water showed that these impact processes have electromagnetic nature.

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